

8T – Electron Propagation

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October 1, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present a new form of the primorial by changing the form of the invariant multiplier, using the nature of the electron and the proven equivalence of the invariant three to the electron itself. The new form could have several possible meanings.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions which are $\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial t} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{g}'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The equation of the Bosonic class is represented by the new form of the wave equation, which is net curvature diverging on the matric tensor. that is by a five-vector. We have proven the invariant three to be the electron by putting it in the fine structure formula. It is considered the electron to each of the higher coupling terms.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V \quad (1.33)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial t_n^2} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2}$$

The key point to is the following, to represent the relation of the electron to the strong interaction, it is possible to use the primorial in the following form:

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

That is to state that the strong interaction even term is ever containing the electron. From the second term and above the electron is propagated out-ward. Since the electron is isomorphic to the Boson of the weak interaction, which can be either particle or a wave, so does the electron possess that particle duality. Given by the wave equation the electron is propagating all across the nuclei, as it is bounded by the bracket. That is important to clarify as it comes to an agreement with the insight of Quantum mechanics.

$$\left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + \gamma_\mu$$

$$8 \rightarrow 2^e \quad (1.25)$$

That new form of the primorial could be analyzed in the following form. The electron is not generated from the second term and above, but was already in existence inside the hadron. This instability, once there can not stay inside the hadron and must propagate outward, in all directions. This instability is bounded to the hadron, unlike the Bosons which are net curvature diverging unbound. Since it is possible to replace the positions of the elements using spin symmetry, there could be unbounded electrons in nature.

$$\left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + \gamma_\mu \rightarrow \left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + \gamma_\mu \right) + (e)_\mu$$

It is possible to express the motion of the electron inside the hadron before it gets propagated if the subscript is preserved.

$$\left(2^e * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + \gamma_\mu \rightarrow \left(2^{e_\mu} * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + \gamma_\mu$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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